

Design and Simulation of a Standalone Solar-Powered Peltier Cooling System for Rural Dairy Applications

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Abstract - Limited access to reliable electricity in rural regions presents a significant barrier to establishing cold storage infrastructure, particularly for preserving perishable commodities such as milk. This paper presents the design and simulation of a standalone solar photovoltaic (PV) system intended to power a Peltier-based milk cooling unit in an off-grid rural collection center. System performance was evaluated using PVsyst simulation software, incorporating long-term climatic data obtained from the Meteonorm database for the selected location. This data enabled accurate assessment of solar resource availability and prediction of system behavior under typical environmental conditions. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed configuration can reliably meet the defined cooling load, confirming its technical feasibility and potential as a sustainable solution for decentralized dairy infrastructure in rural settings.

Keywords: Solar Energy, Renewable Energy, Peltier module, PVsyst Simulation, Standalone system, Rural Dairy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Solar energy has emerged as a viable and sustainable solution for addressing global energy challenges, particularly in regions with high solar potential. As an abundant and renewable resource, solar power offers a decentralized alternative to conventional electricity, making it especially attractive for rural and remote areas where grid access is limited or unreliable.

In India, rural communities form the backbone of the agricultural economy, yet often lack access to reliable energy for essential post-harvest and processing activities. The dairy sector, in particular, faces challenges related to the preservation and handling of perishable milk at village-level collection points. These centers serve as aggregation hubs where farmers deposit milk throughout the day, requiring reliable cooling for extended periods typically up to 10 hours (5am to 10 am) and (4pm to 9pm) before the milk is transported to centralized processing facilities. The absence of adequate cooling during

this holding window can lead to a decline in product quality, reduced earnings for farmers, and inefficiencies in the supply chain.

To address this gap, solar-powered cooling systems offer a viable, clean, and self-sustaining alternative to grid-dependent refrigeration. Among various technologies, thermoelectric (Peltier-based) cooling systems are particularly attractive due to their low maintenance, solid-state operation, and compatibility with direct current (DC) power sources. These systems are well-suited for small-scale applications in rural environments where simplicity, reliability, and autonomy are critical.

In this work, a standalone solar PV system is designed and simulated to operate a Peltier cooling unit at a Rural Milk Collection Center in Dibbapalem village, located in the Visakhapatnam district of Andhra Pradesh, India. The location was selected due to its representative rural setting, dairy activity, and high solar insolation. The proposed system includes a fixed-tilt PV array, lead-acid battery bank configured for short-term energy autonomy, and a maximum power point tracking (MPPT) charge controller. The system's performance is analyzed using PVsyst simulation software, focusing on energy yield, load coverage, and operational reliability under actual environmental conditions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent times, solar photovoltaic (PV) and cooling technologies have demonstrated significant promise in meeting off-grid refrigeration requirements, especially in rural regions. Ravi Kumar et al. [1] developed a standalone solar PV system utilizing PVsyst and METEONORM, focusing on precise simulation, however, they did not validate system under practical performance in real-world scenarios. Hamidreza Najafi and Woodbury [2] investigated the application of thermoelectric (Peltier) modules in cooling systems through MATLAB and genetic algorithm-based optimization, identifying efficiency issues and high operational costs as primary disadvantages.

Anosh S. Dive et al. [3] constructed a solar-powered refrigerator using Peltier modules, observing that despite the design's potential, low thermal efficiency remained a significant limitation.

Soufi Aicha et al. [4] employed PVsyst to simulate PV systems for dairy farm use, but their analysis lacked long-term operational feasibility or environmental sustainability. Nuri Caglayan [5] performed a technical and economic evaluation of a solar-assisted cooling system using PVsyst and METEONORM, yet their study did not provide detailed cost data, risk mitigation analysis, and a comprehensive system evaluation beyond efficiency. Henning Buitendach et al. [6] created a solar-powered Peltier cooling system for vaccine storage, successfully designing the system, but their paper omitted detailed cost analysis, user-side sustainability considerations, and system maintenance implications. P. Pounraja et al. [7] experimentally examined a hybrid solar cooling system using Peltier modules, achieving favorable short-term performance results, but their study did not consider long-term performance degradation, system durability, or scalability in real field conditions.

Although tools like PVsyst and METEONORM have been extensively utilized, many of these studies did not incorporate region-specific solar data crucial for accurate system design in rural Indian areas such as Dibbapalem. Moreover, while solar PV systems and thermoelectric cooling have been individually explored, no previous research has combined Peltier-based cooling with PVsyst-based simulation specifically tailored for milk preservation in rural India. This paper aims to fill that critical gap.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The components chosen and modeled for simulating a standalone solar-powered milk cooling system with a thermoelectric Peltier module include the following:

A. Materials Used

a) Solar PV Module: Trina Solar TSM-320PD14 photovoltaic panels were utilized. Each panel has a capacity of 320Wp, with a V_{mp} of 34.5 V and a V_{oc} of 41.5 V. Three panels were arranged to produce adequate energy for the system's needs.

b) Peltier Module: A TEC1-12706 thermoelectric module was chosen as the system's cooling component. It functions at 12 V DC, drawing a current of roughly 6 A, and offers a cooling capacity of approximately 60 W. Considering its electrical specifications and the projected use for cooling 10 liters of milk, the total energy consumption per day was determined to be 1.22 kWh/day. This figure was utilized as a constant DC load input in the PVsyst simulation to represent the energy needs of the cooling unit under rural field conditions.

c) Battery Storage: A 24 V DC battery system was set up using two 12 V, 120 Ah lead-acid batteries connected in series. This storage system is designed to offer 2 days of autonomy,

Fig. 3.1. Geographical Location of Selected Site

Fig. 3.2. Pv Array Orientation

ensuring continuous cooling even on days with low solar energy production.

d) Charge Controller: A Victron SmartSolar MPPT 100/20 charge controller was chosen to regulate the energy flow between the PV array and the battery. It includes Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) for enhanced efficiency and can manage up to 100 V input and 20 A output.

B. Methodology

A standalone photovoltaic (PV) system was modeled using PVsystV8.0.14 to assess its feasibility for powering a rural milk cooling application. The selected location was Milk Center in Dibbapalem village in Anakapalli Mandalam (17.774°N, 82.9°E), Visakhapatnam district, India (Fig 3.1). Weather data for the site was sourced from the Meteonorm 8.2 (2001–2020) synthetic database integrated within PVsyst. The solar array was configured with a fixed-tilt design facing true south (azimuth of 0°), and a tilt angle of 20°, optimized based on the geographical latitude of the location to ensure year-round solar exposure(Fig 3.2). Environmental shading conditions were accounted for using two models: the distant landscape was simulated using a horizon line with an average elevation of 2.5/degree, while localized obstructions were handled through the software's linear near-shading model using fast table-based calculations. The system was designed to meet a steady electrical

Fig. 3.3. View of Milk Center and Panel Placement on roof

demand modeled after a small-scale milk cooling setup. This included two Peltier modules and their associated cooling fans, each drawing 60W for a duration of 10 hours daily, as well as auxiliary standby loads operating throughout the day. The total estimated energy demand was approximately 1.224kWh per day, modeled as a constant load throughout the year. The PV generator used two Trina Solar TSM-320PD14 modules selected from PVsyst's internal database. Each module was rated at 240 Wp, resulting in a combined system capacity of 480 Wp. These modules were connected in series within a single string configuration. To provide energy storage, a battery bank consisting of six OPzS Solar 70 lead-acid tubular batteries was implemented. Arranged in a 3-series, 2-parallel (3S2P) configuration, the bank operated at 24 V and offered a nominal capacity of 156 Ah, chosen to provide short-term autonomy and support reliability during periods of low solar availability. Energy flow between the PV array and the battery storage system was regulated using a SmartSolar MPPT 100/30 charge controller. This device was capable of handling up to 100 V input voltage and 30 A output current, making it suitable for the voltage and current characteristics of the system. Electrical and environmental losses were incorporated into the model using standard PVsyst parameters with minor adjustments. Soiling losses were estimated at 2%. The simulation was performed over a full annual cycle, considering seasonal solar availability, temperature variations, and shading effects, in order to assess the system's technical performance and suitability for off-grid rural applications.

C. SYSTEM DESIGN CALCULATIONS

This section outlines the fundamental calculations used to size the standalone solar photovoltaic system for powering a Peltier-based milk cooling unit.

1. Load estimation

$$\text{Daily Load (Wh)} = \text{Load Power (W)} \times \text{Operating Hours (h)}$$

$$2. \text{Battery Capacity (Ah)} = \frac{\text{Daily Load (Wh)} \times \text{Autonomy Days}}{\text{System Voltage (V)} \times \text{Depth of Discharge}}$$

$$3. \text{Total PV Modules} = \frac{\text{Expected PV Power (W)} \times 1000}{\text{Panel Wattage (W)}}$$

4. Expected PV power

$$\text{Expected PV Power (W)} = \frac{\text{Total Daily Load (Wh)} \times \text{Overload Factor}}{4 \times 1000}$$

5. Charge controller rating

$$C = \frac{(N \cdot I \cdot V + P) \cdot f_o}{\eta} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- C : Controller size (W)
- N : Number of batteries
- I : Charging current (A)
- V : Battery voltage (V)
- P : Overall load wattage (W)
- f_o : Overload factor
- η : Efficiency of the controller

C. Configuration of System

The rooftop of the milk collection center in Dibbapalem village, Anakapalli district (17.74°N, 82.9°E) (Fig 3.3), was selected as the installation site for the proposed standalone solar photovoltaic system. The building features a single sloped roof, oriented southward (azimuth = 0°), with an inclination of 21°, matching the site latitude to optimize solar energy capture year-round. No shading obstructions were observed around the installation site during the surveyed hours of milk delivery (early morning and evening), ensuring favorable solar access conditions.

A total of 360 monocrystalline solar panels rated at 600 Wp each are planned, with 180 panels per roof surface. The installation will cover 1019m² (13.21×39.44m), maintaining a 0.02m gap between modules. Panel mounting structures will be identically aligned on both sides to ensure uniform orientation. The technical specifications of the panels are provided in Table 1.

A single SmartSolar MPPT 100/30 (24V) controller is employed to manage power flow from the PV array and control battery charging. Its technical specifications are listed in Table 2.

Parameter	Rating
Maximum Power	600Wp
Module Efficiency	29.2V
Voltage at Max Power	29.2 V
Current at Max Power	8.21 A
Open Circuit Voltage	37.4 V
Short Circuit Voltage	8.80 A
Number of Cells	60
Cell Size	156mm * 156mm
Panel Size	1.099m ²

TABLE I
TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS OF PANEL(TSM-320PD1)

Parameter	Rating
Nominal Battery Voltage	24V
MPPT Voltage Range	29-90 V
Max PV Input Voltage	100 V
Max PV Input Power	800 W
Max Charging Current	30 A
Max PV Input Current	30 A
Nominal Efficiency	96%
Max Efficiency	98%

TABLE II
TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS OF INVERTER(VICTRON/SMARTSOLAR MPPT)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the simulation results of the standalone PV system using PVsyst, with detailed analysis of system performance, energy balance, shading effects, and storage reliability.

A. Horizon and Shading Analysis

The simulation site features a relatively flat horizon with an average elevation angle of 2.5°, resulting in minimal obstruction to solar radiation. Far shading and near shading losses were estimated at 0.2% and 0.1%, respectively. These values indicate that the installation location offers good solar accessibility throughout the year. The shading environment is further visualized through the horizon profile and the iso-shading diagram shown in Fig. 4.1 and Fig. 4.2.

B. PV Array Performance

The system consists of two monocrystalline panels totaling 480/Wp. Under standard conditions, this represents peak

Fig. 4.1. Azimuth Diagram

Fig. 4.2. Iso-shading Diagram

Fig. 4.3. Performance Ratio

output, but real-world factors such as temperature, wiring resistance, and soiling contribute to energy losses. Notably, temperature effects were the most significant. After accounting for all array-level losses, the system achieved a Performance Ratio (PR) of 50.51% (Figure 4.3) which is typical for small standalone systems with battery constraints. The cumulative energy losses are summarized in the loss diagram in Fig 4.4.

Fig. 4.4. Loss Diagram

Fig. 4.5. Monthly average daily solar input and load

Balances and main results									
	GlobHor kWh/m²	GlobEff kWh/m²	E_Avail kWh	E_Used kWh	E_Miss kWh	E_User kWh	E_Load kWh	SolFrac	99%
January	138.3	159.4	66.06	25.27	0.000	37.94	37.94	1.000	
February	143.1	155.4	63.98	28.00	0.000	34.27	34.27	1.000	
March	172.4	173.5	70.14	30.06	0.000	37.94	37.94	1.000	
April	160.6	169.9	68.35	29.72	0.000	36.72	36.72	1.000	
May	175.9	156.3	62.64	22.78	0.000	37.94	37.94	1.000	
June	138.2	119.9	47.65	9.18	0.000	36.72	36.72	1.000	
July	131.5	115.3	45.83	6.15	0.121	37.82	37.94	0.997	
August	132.1	120.3	47.94	9.45	0.000	37.94	37.94	1.000	
September	134.9	131.1	52.52	15.18	1.218	35.50	36.72	0.967	
October	147.6	153.6	62.20	22.26	0.000	37.94	37.94	1.000	
November	128.7	144.4	59.70	21.27	0.000	36.72	36.72	1.000	
December	129.1	149.1	61.93	22.14	0.000	37.94	37.94	1.000	
Year	1753.5	1750.2	708.75	240.49	1.339	445.42	446.76	0.997	

Legends
 GlobHor Global horizontal irradiation
 GlobEff Effective Global, corr. for IAM and shadings
 E_Avail Available Solar Energy
 E_Used Unused energy (battery full)
 E_Miss Missing energy
 E_User Energy supplied to the user
 E_Load Energy need of the user (Load)
 SolFrac Solar fraction (E_Used / E_Load)

Fig. 4.6. Monthly energy and Solar contribution

C. Battery Storage Performance

A lead-acid battery bank is employed to facilitate off-grid functionality, set up to provide adequate autonomy for essential daily energy needs. The storage system is regulated by state-of-charge thresholds to maintain battery health. Simulation outcomes reveal minimal battery losses and a moderate rate of charge-discharge cycles, indicating stable long-term performance. The battery consistently contributed to system efficiency throughout the year.

D. Energy Yield and System Balance

The annual solar energy available at the location was adequate to fulfill the anticipated cooling load. Some of this energy remained unused due to battery constraints, while only a small portion of energy demand was unmet. Overall, the system achieved a Solar Fraction of 99.70% demonstrating its capability to supply nearly the entire load. Monthly fluctuations in generation and consumption are depicted in Fig. 4.5, with detailed values provided in Table 4.6 .

E. System Reliability

The system was designed to offer two days of autonomy, ensuring a steady energy supply even during periods of low irradiation. The minimal energy supply shortfall and extremely low loss of load percentage highlight the reliability of the configuration for rural standalone applications such as dairy operations.

5. CONCLUSION

In this study, a standalone solar photovoltaic (PV) system was designed and simulated to power a Peltier-based milk

cooling unit in a rural collection center located in Dibbapalem village, Visakhapatnam district. The system was developed to operate independently of the utility grid and to provide reliable cooling for up to 10 hours per day, accommodating milk delivered by local farmers prior to transport.

Using PVsyst software, the proposed configuration—comprising a 480 Wp fixed-tilt PV array, a 24 V 156 Ah lead-acid battery bank, and a maximum power point tracking (MPPT) charge controller—was evaluated under realistic climatic conditions specific to Dibbapalem village in Visakhapatnam district. The simulation outcomes validated the technical viability of the system, achieving a solar fraction of 99.70%, a performance ratio of 50.51%, and an annual unmet load of just 1.34 kWh. Battery operation remained within recommended cycling and depth-of-discharge limits throughout the year, confirming the system’s reliability and operational resilience.

The outcomes confirm that solar-powered cooling can serve as an effective solution for improving cold-chain continuity in off-grid dairy networks. By enabling stable milk storage at collection points, the proposed system contributes to better handling practices, reduced product degradation, and greater income stability for rural farming communities.

Looking ahead, the system holds strong potential for future expansion. Integrating additional loads such as lighting or automation, applying data monitoring for performance optimization, or scaling the system for use in larger dairy clusters can further enhance its utility. This work provides a practical foundation for deploying decentralized solar energy solutions in rural agricultural infrastructure.

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